

EFFECT OF COBALT DOPING ON STRUCTURAL, OPTICAL, AND PHOTOCATALYTIC PROPERTIES OF ZNS NANOSTRUCTURES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14730715>

ABSTRACT

Cobalt (1% and 3%) -doped ZnS nanoparticles were synthesized through co-precipitation technique. The resultant nanoparticles have been analyzed using UV- visible (UV-Vis) and Fourier transform infrared radiation (FTIR). It was found that absorbance increased as Co-doping increased. The optical band gap decreased as the Co content increased, and the band gap varied with the cobalt doping concentration. Energy band gap was found 0.56 eV for 1% and 0.37 eV for 3% doping. Both the samples' FT-IR spectra were captured in the 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} regions. The doping of cobalt source contributed to the sulphate stretching vibration. As a result, it is verified that the sulphate group was present in the synthesized NPs. It is also observed that agglomerates number appears to decrease in the existence of cobalt content which is good for optical and electronic applications.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Co-precipitation, Absorbance, concentration, Optical, Agglomerates.

INTRODUCTION

Because of its numerous uses in electrical and optical devices during the past 20 years, zero-dimensional structures of semiconductor nanoparticles (NPs) doped with transition metals have drawn a lot of interest [1]. Research on transition metal-doped chalcogenide nanomaterials has attracted a lot of attention lately [2]. There are numerous uses for transition metal-doped ZnS nanostructures in the fields of spintronics, solar cells, light-emitting diodes, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and lasers [3]. Scientists and researchers have been very interested in nanoscale materials because of its unique and innovative properties, such include quantum confinement and a large exterior to

dimension ratio [4]. Many physical and optical characteristics of ZnS doped with Cd, Co, Ga, Cu, Ni, Bi, and Fe have recently been effectively investigated [5]. The broad bandgap characteristic of II–VI semiconductor materials and their potential optoelectronic applications have recently sparked a lot of technological interest. In the past few years, researchers have also been drawn to semiconductor nanoparticles because of their unique electrical and optical properties, which set them apart from bulk semiconductors [6]. The optical, electrical, and catalytic behaviours of semiconductor nanoparticles have been the subject of numerous studies in the past few years. One of the class II–VI semiconducting materials

is zinc sulphide (ZnS). Among the potential uses are phosphor, light-emitting diode (LED), sensor [7], and laser [8]. By adding specific dopants to its lattice, semiconductor chalcogenides' structure, optical characteristics, and magnetic properties can be adjusted [6]. Co appears to be a highly preferred doping element that can improve the optical properties, according to a lot of study [9]. In general, Co doped ZnS offers novel prospects for full-colour luminescence in the UV-visible spectrum, which is employed for a number of purposes, including research [10]. Because of the Co d-orbital's mixing with the II-VI materials' valence and conduction bands, CDZS showed a greater coupling [9]. Co²⁺-doped ZnS nanoparticles are particularly interesting in addition to ZnS nanoparticles because of their appealing distinctive qualities for use in light-emitting diodes, lasers [11], sensors [12], bio-devices, infrared windows, flat panel displays, and phosphors [13]. Even though the ZnS:Cu system for optoelectronic devices has been the subject of numerous research articles, thorough structural and optical analyses are still omitted necessitating additional study to fully comprehend its optoelectronic characteristics [14]. Numerous recent studies have addressed the suitability of semiconductor materials for optoelectronic applications, whose energy band gap varies depending on the dopant concentration [1]. Controlling the surface area, shape, and internal structure of materials to achieve good performance is an important work. Due to its outstanding stability, ZnS is a good choice for a host material. The electrochemical performance of ZnS nanostructures may alter when dopants are added [15]. An attractive platform for analysing the optical and magnetic properties is Co-doped nanocrystalline ZnS [16]. Transition metal-doped ZnS have been referred for improved photocatalytic activity [17]. The synthesis of Co-doped ZnS nanoparticles using the chemical co-precipitation method is presented in this research. This method is employed due of its inexpensive cost and ease of achieving the dopant concentration [13]. The structural and optical properties of the synthesized nanoparticles were carried out by Fourier transform infrared radiation (FTIR) and UV-Visible spectroscopy (UV- Vis).

The optical and structural studies of mentioned nanoparticles are discussed in this article.

2. Experimental

2.1 Chemical used

All of the chemicals were bought by Sigma-Aldrich company. All analytical-grade reactants and solvents were used without further purification. Cobalt chloride (CoCl₂), zinc chloride (ZnCl₂), and thiourea (NH₂CSNH₂) have all been utilised as sources of sulphur, cobalt, and zinc, respectively [6].

2.2 Synthesis of Co doped ZnS

Cobalt doped ZnS nanoparticles (1% and 3%) were synthesized at room temperature by co-precipitation technique. This method is preferred to synthesize nanomaterials in existing literature [18]. Distilled water has been used as a solvent. The synthesis of Co doped ZnS nanoparticles has been carried out precisely as described in the literature [13]. To achieve desired compositions of 1 and 3 at% of cobalt, appropriate quantities of compounds were weighed in accordance with the stoichiometry [19]. In a standard process, 200 millilitres of distilled water were used to dissolve zinc chloride and thiourea in the necessary concentration. Cobalt chloride is added to the mentioned combination in the appropriate concentration for cobalt doping [3]. Zinc chloride was allowed to dissolve completely in distilled water under vigorous magnetic stirring until a clear, homogenous solution was obtained. After that, the mixture was stirred for thirty minutes. An equimolar solution of thiourea was then added slowly to the zinc chloride solution. When thiourea solution was added, a milky mixture formed, which was a sign that zinc sulphide nanoparticles were being produced. The thiourea solution was added drop by drop until precipitates developed after the zinc sulphide solution was stirred for an hour with 1% cobalt chloride to dope the ZnS nanoparticles [13]. To increase the pH and make the solution a strong base, pallets of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were added. The precipitates were centrifuged and then cleaned multiple times with distilled water before being dried in an oven that was set to 100 degrees Celsius [20]. Cobalt-doped zinc sulphide

nanoparticles were prepared by grinding the dry sample. Similarly, samples of zinc sulfide doped with cobalt 3% were also prepared.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Optical analysis

An appropriate technique for examining the effects of co-doping and impurity defects on the optical characteristics of ZnS nanoparticles is UV-visible spectroscopy, as co-doped ZnS nanoparticles differ optically from pure ZnS [21]. The UV-Visible absorption spectra of Co-doped

(1% and 3%) ZnS nanoparticles are shown in Fig 3.1 (a, b). It was observed that as co-doping increased absorbance improved [22]. The published research indicates that a variety of factors, such as particle size and deficits in grain structure, also affect absorbance. The absorbance versus wavelength graph shows that the lowest absorption occurs at approximately 380 nm. The wavelength causes the absorbance spectra to gradually increase in the visible range after rapidly declining in the UV region [9].

Figure 3.1 (a, b) uv vis absorbance spectra.

Wood and Tauc's equation give the relation among the incident photon energy ($h\nu$) and the absorption coefficient (α).

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2} = A (h\nu - E_g)$$

E_g stands for the material's energy bandgap, h for Planck's constant, ν for photon frequency, exponent n for the type of transition, and A for constant. Transitions with $n = 1/2$ are directly permitted, those with $n = 2$ are indirectly permitted, those with $n = 3/2$ are directly forbidden, and those with $n = 3$ are indirectly forbidden. Figure 3.2 (a, b) shows the Tauc plot of

ZnS nanoparticles. A direct transition is evident from the graph's linear shape. The bandgap energy of the samples is obtained by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ versus Energy = $h\nu$. The straight portion of the curve on the $h\nu$ axis is linearly fitted to yield the energy band gap value [13]. Researchers speculated that the decrease in the band gap for Co-doped ZnS nanoparticles would be due to the sp-d exchange interaction between the band electrons and the localised d electrons of Co^{2+} ions. Consequently, co-doped ZnS nanoparticles produced by the co-precipitation method have better properties for practical applications [13].

Figure 3.2 (a, b) Energy band gap spectra by Tauc method.

3.2 Functional group analysis

The existence of the several functional molecular groups integrated on the synthesised nanostructured material has been effectively demonstrated by the Fourier Transform Infra-red spectroscopy (FT-IR) technique, which has also been used to confirm the production of metal oxide [22]. All of the samples' FT-IR spectra were captured in the 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} regions [23]. According to the graph 3.3(a, b), the following absorption zones were identified: 3451 cm^{-1} and 3486 cm^{-1} . The broad and intense absorption spectra found in Region I, which have been acquired at the wave numbers, are caused by the O-H stretching and bending vibrations of

chemically adsorbed hydroxyl groups water content. The band in area II, which is attributed to the O-H bending vibration of distorted water molecules, appeared at 1599 cm^{-1} and 1606 cm^{-1} [24]. The significant absorption peak in Regions III and IV, which was observed in those corresponding bands at approximately 1041 cm^{-1} and 896 cm^{-1} , indicates the inclusion of a stretched sulphate group. In this work, the sulphate stretching vibration was made possible by the $(\text{NH}_2\text{CSNH}_2)$ thiourea. The band at 710 cm^{-1} and 715 cm^{-1} give Zn-Co-S vibrations effect [8]. These results are well matched with existing research given in table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Observed Molecular vibrations for Cobalt doped ZnS (1% and 3%) Wave number(cm^{-1})

Cobalt doped ZnS (1%)	Cobalt doped ZnS (3%)	Vibrational assignments
3451 cm^{-1}	3486 cm^{-1}	O-H Stretching
1599 cm^{-1}	1606 cm^{-1}	O-H Bending
1041 cm^{-1}	1041 cm^{-1}	Sulphate Group
896 cm^{-1}	900 cm^{-1}	Sulphate Group
710 cm^{-1}	715 cm^{-1}	Zn-Co-S Bonding

Figure 3.3 (a, b) FTIR graph for cobalt (1% and 3%) doped ZnS

Conclusion:

At room temperature, Co-doped (1% and 2%) ZnS nanoparticles were synthesized using the co-precipitation method. The prepared sample particle sizes estimated inside the nano range. Additionally, a decrease in the amount of agglomerates tends to occur when cobalt content is present, making it suitable for optical and electronic applications. It was found that the Cobalt doped at 1% ZnS nanoparticles' bandgap was 0.56 eV, and that this value redshifted as the quantity of Co increased. The energy bandgap becomes 0.37 eV. The addition of varying concentrations of Co^{2+} from 1% doping to 2% doping caused the FT-IR bands to shift slightly towards the lower wavenumber region. The synthesized nanoparticles have potential as materials for optoelectronic and spintronic devices, according to the results.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. ShunmugaSundaram, R. Shanmugam, A. Elangovan, L. B. Chandrasekhar, K. Gurushankar, and G. Arivazhagan, 'Structural and Optical Studies on Cr-Doped ZnS Nanoparticles Prepared by Flat Co-precipitation Method', *Braz J Phys*, vol. 54, no. 4, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s13538-024-01465-3.
- [2] S. Sambasivam, B. Sathyaseelan, D. Raja Reddy, B. K. Reddy, and C. K. Jayasankar, 'ESR and photoluminescence properties of Cu doped ZnS nanoparticles', *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 1503–1506, Dec. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2008.05.009.
- [3] S. Kumar and N. K. Verma, 'Room Temperature Magnetism in Cobalt-Doped ZnS Nanoparticles', *J Supercond Nov Magn*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 137–142, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10948-014-2823-6.

- [4] N. A. Shad *et al.*, ‘Zn₃(VO₄)₂/Bi₂WO₆ composite based versatile platform for cotinine sensing and latent fingerprints development by using multiple modalities’, *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, vol. 301, p. 117203, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.mseb.2024.117203.
- [5] S. Vijayan, G. Umadevi, R. Mariappan, M. Narayanan, B. Narayanamoorthy, and S. Kandasamy, ‘WITHDRAWN: High luminescence efficiency of Copper doped Zinc Sulfide (Cu: ZnS) nanoparticles towards LED applications’, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, p. S2214785320388222, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.11.214.
- [6] Z. K. Heiba, M. B. Mohamed, A. M. El-naggar, and A. A. Albassam, ‘Effect of Mg and Cu doping on structural, optical, electronic, and thermal properties of ZnS quantum dots’, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron*, vol. 31, no. 23, pp. 21342–21354, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10854-020-04647-2.
- [7] H. Z. Mahmood *et al.*, ‘Plasmon-Based Label-Free Biosensor Using Gold Nanosphere for Dengue Detection’, *Crystals*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 1340, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.3390/cryst11111340. ISSN (E): 3006-7030 (P) 3006-7022
- [8] M. Jothibas, M. Elayaraja, E. Paulson, S. Srinivasan, and B. A. Kumar, ‘Dynamic photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants employing co-doped ZnS nanoparticles synthesized via solid state reaction method’, *Surfaces and Interfaces*, vol. 33, p. 102249, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.surfin.2022.102249.
- [9] R. Nasrin, L. Khan, M. O. Haq, M. Mohiuddin, and H. Kabir, ‘Surface topography, structural, optical and dc electrical behaviors of pristine and Co-doped ZnS thin films’, *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. e29337, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29337.
- [10] Y. Meng, R. Zhou, H. Dinçer, S. Yüksel, and C. Wang, ‘Analysis of inventive problem-solving capacities for renewable energy storage investments’, *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 4779–4791, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.06.086.
- [11] F. Meng, J. Yin, Y.-Q. Duan, Z.-H. Yuan, and L.-J. Bie, ‘Co-precipitation synthesis and gas-sensing properties of ZnO hollow sphere with porous shell’, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, vol. 156, no. 2, pp. 703–708, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2011.02.022.
- [12] G. S. Harish and P. Sreedhara Reddy, ‘Synthesis and characterization of Ce, Cu co-doped ZnS nanoparticles’, *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, vol. 473, pp. 48–53, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.physb.2015.04.042.
- [13] V. V. Jadhavar, V. D. Mote, and B. S. Munde, ‘Study of structural, optical, and paramagnetic properties of Zn_{1-x}CoxS nanoparticles prepared via co-precipitation’, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron*, vol. 31, no. 20, pp. 17297–17306, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s10854-020-04284-9.
- [14] R. S. R. Mummadi and K. Shaik, ‘Structural, Optical, and Electrical Properties of Cu-Doped ZnS Nanoparticles Prepared by Solid-State Reaction’, *Braz J Phys*, vol. 54, no. 3, p. 78, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s13538-024-01457-3.
- [15] I. Hussain *et al.*, ‘Binder-free cupric-ion containing zinc sulfide nanoplates-like structure for flexible energy storage devices’, *Chemosphere*, vol. 314, p. 137660, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.137660.
- [16] B. Poornaprakash, D. Amaranatha Reddy, G. Murali, N. Madhusudhana Rao, R. P. Vijayalakshmi, and B. K. Reddy, ‘Composition dependent room temperature ferromagnetism and PL intensity of cobalt doped ZnS nanoparticles’, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 577, pp. 79–85, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.04.106.
- [17] R. Wang, H. Liang, J. Hong, and Z. Wang, ‘Hydrothermal synthesis of cobalt-doped ZnS for efficient photodegradation of methylene blue’, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A:*

- Chemistry*, vol. 325, pp. 62–67, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jphotochem.2016.03.036.
- [18] A. P. Jeyakumari, M. Sumathi, N. Thirumagal, and M. U. Kumar, ‘Chemical Precipitation Synthesis of Fe, Ni, and Co Doped Zinc Sulphide Nanoparticles’, *IOSR JAP*, vol. 01, no. 01, pp. 64–70, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.9790/4861-17002016470.
- [19] A. Divya, B. K. Reddy, S. Sambasivam, K. Siva Kumar, and P. Sreedhara Reddy, ‘Structural and optical characterization of ZnS nanoparticles co-doped with Mn and Te’, *Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 541–545, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.physe.2011.09.010.
- [20] B. Poornaprakash, U. Chalapathi, M. Kumar, S. Ramu, S. V. Prabhakar Vattikuti, and S.-H. Park, ‘Enhanced photocatalytic degradation and hydrogen evolution of ZnS nanoparticles by (Co, Er) co-doping’, *Materials Letters*, vol. 273, p. 127887, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matlet.2020.127887.
- [21] B. Sreenivasulu, S. Venkatramana Reddy, and P. Venkateswara Reddy, ‘Structural, optical and magnetic properties of (Cu, Ni) co-doped ZnS nanoparticles’, *J Mater Sci: Mater Electron*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 251–259, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10854-017-7911-5.
- [22] E. S. Agorku, M. A. Mamo, B. B. Mamba, A. C. Pandey, and A. K. Mishra, ‘Cobalt-doped ZnS-reduced graphene oxide nanocomposite as an advanced photocatalytic material’, *J Porous Mater*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 47–56, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10934-014-9871-y.
- [23] N. A. Shad *et al.*, ‘Fabrication of Spike-Like Spherical Iron Manganite Nanoparticles for the Augmented Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue Dye’, *J. Electron. Mater.*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 900–909, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11664-021-09371-z.
- [24] M. Sankar, M. Jothibas, A. Muthuvel, A. Rajeshwari, and S. J. Jeyakumar, ‘Structural, optical and Photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes by sol gel prepared Ni doped CdS nanoparticles’, *Surfaces and Interfaces*, vol. 21, p. 100775, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.surfin.2020.100775.